

Conference Abstract

The genus *Albinaria* Vest, 1867 (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Clausiliidae), part II: Albania, Greece, Turkey and Lebanon (except the islands)

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Abstract

The genus *Albinaria* Vest, 1864 (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Clausiliidae) live on limestone rocks and show a remarkable diversity in the eastern Mediterranean region. This is mainly caused by the tendency of these populations to split up into local forms with highly restricted areas of distribution. This phenomenon is also furthered by geological and environmental factors and, often, by geographic isolation.

In this work, we present further results on our studies on the genus *Albinaria*. An updated check-list of the populations coming from Albania, Greece, Turkey and Lebanon (except the islands) is provided and most of these populations are illustrated.

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